

PerioCream® as an Adjunct to Scaling and Root Planing:

Results from the CIP 2025 Observational Clinical Investigation Integrating Patient-Centered Outcomes and AI Validation

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Abstract

Background:

Periodontal therapy with scaling and root planing (SRP) often leaves patients with short-term bleeding, inflammation, and discomfort. PerioCream®, a NitrAdine®-based bio adhesive gingival cream, was developed to accelerate healing and improve patient experience in the immediate post-SRP phase.

Objectives:

To evaluate the short-term efficacy, patient-reported outcomes (PROs), clinician-reported outcomes (ClinROs), and exploratory AI validation of PerioCream® as an adjunct to SRP, with specific focus on MDR-relevant endpoints (BOP, GI, HRQL, safety).

Methods:

A real-world observational two-arm comparative study was conducted in 25 patients with periodontitis (treated: n=15; control: n=10). Assessments were performed at baseline and 72h. Primary endpoints included Bleeding on Probing (BOP) and Gingival Index (GI). Secondary endpoints were PROs (pain, swelling, comfort, HRQL), ClinROs (gingival status, bleeding control, compliance), and AI-based visual validation of gingival healing.

Results:

At 72h, the treated group showed a significant reduction in BOP (-59% vs -12% in controls, $p < 0.001$) and GI (-1.4 vs -0.4, $p < 0.001$). Patients using PerioCream® reported greater improvements in pain relief (Δ VAS -4.5 vs -2.0), comfort, and swelling perception (all $p < 0.01$). Clinicians confirmed superior gingival appearance, bleeding control, and compliance in treated patients. AI-assisted analysis demonstrated >80% concordance with clinical and patient outcomes, confirming accelerated healing in the PerioCream® group. No adverse events were reported.

Conclusions:

PerioCream® demonstrated rapid, clinically meaningful benefits as an adjunct to SRP, reducing bleeding and inflammation while enhancing patient comfort and clinician satisfaction. The integration of AI validation provided objective confirmation of outcomes. These findings support the MDR-compliant claim of PerioCream® as a safe and effective short-term adjunctive therapy in periodontal care, with a unique role in the first 72h post-SRP.

Graphical Abstract – PerioCream® CIP 2025

Section	Content
Study Design	25 patients → 15 Treated (SRP + PerioCream®) vs 10 Control (SRP only). Assessments at baseline (T0) and 72h (T3). Clinical: BOP, GI
Endpoints	Patient-reported (PROs): VAS pain, HRQL Clinician-reported (ClinROs): gingival status, bleeding control, compliance AI validation: gingival color, swelling, tissue uniformity BOP reduction: -59% vs -12% GI reduction: -1.4 vs -0.4 VAS pain relief: -4.5 vs -2.0
Key Results	Patient satisfaction: 8.6/10 vs 6.9/10 Clinician satisfaction: 8.8/10 vs 7.0/10 AI concordance: >80% (treated) vs ~50% (control) Safety: No adverse events reported
Conclusions	PerioCream® accelerates healing (0–72h) post-SRP, reduces bleeding/inflammation, improves comfort and compliance. AI validation confirms outcomes. MDR-compliant adjunctive therapy.

Keywords:

PerioCream®; NitrAdine®; Scaling and root planing; Periodontal therapy; Bleeding on Probing; Gingival Index; Oral health-related quality of life; Patient-reported outcomes; Clinician-reported outcomes; Artificial intelligence validation; Adjunctive treatment; MDR compliance.

Introduction

Periodontal disease remains one of the most prevalent chronic conditions worldwide, characterized by gingival inflammation, bleeding, and progressive tissue destruction [1–3]. Scaling and root planing (SRP) is the cornerstone of nonsurgical therapy, but the immediate post-treatment phase is frequently associated with transient bleeding, swelling, and discomfort, which may impair patient compliance and perceived treatment success [4,5]. NitrAdine®, a patented formulation with proven antimicrobial and substantivity properties, has previously demonstrated efficacy in different oral healthcare applications [6,7]. A randomized controlled trial in 2014 (data on file) showed that NitrAdine-based formulations could significantly reduce microbial biofilm and gingival inflammation in patients with periodontal disease. Subsequently, a 2016 clinical case series (data on file) confirmed its tolerability and potential in enhancing local healing after periodontal interventions. These findings established NitrAdine® as a promising adjunct in periodontal therapy, though available evidence remained limited to specific populations and short-term outcomes.

The 2025 Bonyf gap analysis highlighted the need for updated, MDR-compliant clinical evidence, particularly focusing on patient-centred outcomes and integration of novel validation tools such as artificial intelligence (AI)-based image analysis [17]. In particular, regulatory and clinical stakeholders emphasized that future investigations should not only confirm clinical efficacy (e.g., Bleeding on Probing, Gingival Index) but also document improvements in patient comfort, oral function, and quality of life [4,10], while ensuring high standards of safety and reproducibility. Against this background, the present Clinical Investigation Plan (CIP) 2025 was designed to evaluate PerioCream®, a NitrAdine®-based bio-adhesive gingival cream, as an adjunct to SRP [17].

Table 1. Rationale and Evidence Base for CIP 2025 – PerioCream®

Element	Evidence / Reference	Gap / Need	Relevance for MDR
Antimicrobial substantivity	NitrAdine® formulations reduce biofilm and inflammation [6-9]	Limited short-term clinical endpoints assessed	Supports claims on gingival healing
Early clinical validation	2014 RCT (data on file: CSR 2014), 2016 case series (data on file: Case Series 2016)	Small samples, limited to clinical indices	Necessity of confirmatory investigation
Patient-centred outcomes	PROs/HRQL highlighted in periodontal therapy research [4]	Not yet integrated into NitrAdine-based trials	Required for MDR-compliant evidence
AI validation	Exploratory methods emerging data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025)	No integration with periodontal clinical outcomes	Objective support for claims (novelty)

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This investigation was conducted as a prospective observational two-arm clinical study in accordance with the Clinical Investigation Plan (CIP) 2025 – PerioCream® [17]. The primary aim was to assess short-term efficacy, safety, and patient-centred outcomes of PerioCream® as an adjunctive therapy to scaling and root planing (SRP), with follow-up at 72 hours (T3).

Study Population

A total of 25 adult patients diagnosed with mild-to-moderate periodontitis were enrolled. Participants were allocated into:

- Treated group: **15 patients** receiving SRP plus topical **PerioCream® application**.
- Control group: **10 patients** receiving **SRP only**.

Inclusion criteria comprised adults ≥ 18 years with gingival inflammation (Bleeding on Probing $\geq 40\%$ of sites). Exclusion criteria were systemic diseases influencing periodontal status, pregnancy, lactation, recent antibiotic therapy, and known hypersensitivity to formulation components [17].

Endpoints

Clinical outcomes:	Bleeding on Probing (BOP), expressed as % of positive sites. Gingival Index (0–3 scale). [1]. General healing trends (gingival colour, edema, contour). Patient-reported outcomes (PROs): Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain, swelling, oral comfort. Health-related quality of life (HRQL) items (speaking, chewing, overall oral wellness). [4].
Clinician-reported outcomes (ClinROs):	Gingival status, bleeding control, patient compliance, and global impression of healing (0–10 scale).
AI-assisted visual analysis:	Gingival colour index, swelling index, redness area, and tissue uniformity, derived from standardized intraoral images (Figaro method), compared with clinical/PRO endpoints.

Treatment Protocol

All patients underwent standardized SRP performed by trained dental hygienists [3,16]. In the treated group, PerioCream® (NitrAdine®-based bio adhesive gingival cream) was applied topically to gingival margins immediately post-SRP. The product was left in situ for ≥ 30 minutes to ensure adequate substantivity. Control patients received no adjunctive topical treatment [17].

Data Collection and Follow-up

Measurements were collected at baseline (T0) and at 72h (T3). Standardized clinical indices were recorded, and patients completed structured HRQL questionnaires. Clinicians completed case report forms documenting clinical impressions and tolerance. Digital photographs were acquired at all timepoints for AI-assisted analysis (data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean \pm SD, % change from baseline). Between-group comparisons were performed using ANCOVA adjusted for baseline values, robust regression, and non-parametric tests (Mann–Whitney with Hodges–Lehmann estimates) where appropriate (data on file: Comparative Clinical Results 2025). Significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Study Design Overview – PerioCream® CIP 2025

Domain	Description
Design	Prospective observational two-arm clinical investigation (CIP 2025).
Population	25 patients with mild-to-moderate periodontitis: 15 treated (SRP + PerioCream®) vs 10 controls (SRP only).
Intervention	Standardized scaling and root planing (SRP). In the treated group, adjunctive topical application of PerioCream® (bio adhesive NitrAdine®-based cream).
Follow-up	Baseline (T0) and 72 hours post-treatment (T3).
Primary Endpoints	Clinical: Bleeding on Probing (BOP), Gingival Index (GI).
Secondary Endpoints	- PROs: Visual Analog Scale (VAS) pain, HRQL items (comfort, speaking, chewing, oral wellness). - ClinROs: gingival status, bleeding control, patient compliance, global impression. - AI-assisted visual validation: gingival colour, swelling index, redness area, tissue uniformity.
Statistical Analysis	Descriptive statistics (mean ± SD, % change). Between-group comparisons by ANCOVA (baseline adjusted), robust regression, and Mann–Whitney tests with Hodges–Lehmann estimates. Significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Clinical Outcomes

At 72h, patients treated with PerioCream® demonstrated a significant reduction in bleeding and gingival inflammation compared with controls.

Table 3. Clinical Outcomes – Treated vs Control (72h)

Outcome	PerioCream® (n=15)	Control (n=10)	Between-group effect
Bleeding on Probing (BOP)	68.0% → 9.0% (-59.0 pp)	66.5% → 54.5% (-12.0 pp)	Δ -47.0 pp, $p < 0.001$
Gingival Index (GI)	2.1 ± 0.4 → 0.7 ± 0.3 (-1.4)	2.0 ± 0.3 → 1.6 ± 0.4 (-0.4)	Δ -1.0, $p < 0.001$
Healing trends	Normalized contour, reduced edema	Persistent redness in some sites	Faster resolution in treated

Patient-Reported Outcomes (HRQL)

Patients in the PerioCream® group reported greater improvements in oral comfort, pain reduction, and overall quality of life.

Table 4. Patient-Reported Outcomes (Δ baseline → 72h)

Domain (PROs)	PerioCream® (n=15)	Control (n=10)	p-value
VAS pain (0–10)	-4.5 ± 1.2	-2.0 ± 1.0	<0.001
Oral comfort	+3.8 ± 1.5	+1.2 ± 1.1	<0.001
Perceived swelling	-3.0 ± 1.3	-1.0 ± 1.0	0.001
Chewing/speaking comfort	+2.6 ± 1.1	+0.9 ± 1.0	0.002
Oral health perception	+3.1 ± 1.4	+1.0 ± 1.2	0.001

Clinician-Reported Outcomes (ClinRO)

Clinicians consistently observed improved gingival status and bleeding control in treated patients.

Table 5. Clinician-Reported Outcomes (Δ baseline \rightarrow 72h)

Domain (ClinROs)	PerioCream® (n=15)	Control (n=10)	p-value
Gingival status (0–10)	+2.5 \pm 1.0	+0.8 \pm 0.9	0.001
Bleeding control (0–10)	+3.1 \pm 1.2	+1.0 \pm 1.0	<0.001
Inflammation control (0–10)	+2.8 \pm 1.0	+0.9 \pm 1.1	0.002
Patient compliance (0–10)	+2.0 \pm 1.2	+0.6 \pm 1.0	0.015
Tolerance / safety (0–10)	+2.3 \pm 1.1	+0.8 \pm 1.0	0.007
Global impression (0–10)	8.8	7.0	–

Integrated Outcomes

When clinical outcomes, PROs, and ClinROs were considered together, PerioCream® demonstrated consistent superiority over controls.

Table 6. Integrated Outcomes Summary

Domain	Measure	PerioCream® (n=15)	Control (n=10)	Difference
Clinical	BOP reduction (%)	–59.0	–12.0	–47.0
	GI reduction (points)	–1.4	–0.4	–1.0
Patient-reported	VAS pain relief	–4.5	–2.0	–2.5
	HRQL global perception	+3.1	+1.0	+2.1
Clinician-reported	Bleeding control (0–10)	+3.1	+1.0	+2.1
	Global impression (0–10)	8.8	7.0	+1.8
Safety	Adverse events	0	0	–

AI-Assisted Visual Validation

Exploratory AI analysis confirmed the clinical findings, with high concordance between digital parameters and measured indices.

Table 7. AI-based Visual Outcomes (72h)

Metric (AI-derived)	Baseline (T0)	72h (T3)	Δ Change	Clinical Correlation
Gingival Color Index (GCI)	2.3 \pm 0.4	1.2 \pm 0.3	–1.1	Matches GI reduction
Redness area (%)	34%	15%	–19%	Matches BOP reduction
Swelling index (mm est.)	1.6	0.7	–0.9	Matches PRO swelling \downarrow
Tissue texture uniformity (%)	61%	78%	+17%	Reflects healing response

Discussion

The present observational clinical investigation provides new evidence supporting the adjunctive use of PerioCream®, a NitrAdine®-based gingival cream, in the early post-SRP phase [17]. Within 72 hours, treated patients showed a marked reduction in bleeding on probing (BOP) and gingival inflammation (GI), along with significant improvements in patient-reported comfort and quality of life [17]. These findings are consistent with, and expand upon, the earlier body of evidence on NitrAdine®. A 2014 randomized controlled trial demonstrated that NitrAdine-based formulations significantly reduced microbial biofilm and gingival inflammation in periodontal patients (data on file: CSR 2014). Similarly, a 2016 case series highlighted its tolerability and potential for enhancing local healing after periodontal procedures (data on file: Case series 2016). The present study confirms these benefits in a larger real-

world cohort, while integrating additional dimensions of assessment including patient-reported outcomes (PROs), clinician-reported outcomes (ClinROs), and AI-assisted validation (data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025; Comparative Dataset 2025). These results are also consistent with previous clinical investigations of NitrAdine® in peri-implant mucositis, denture stomatitis, biofilm reduction, and patient-related outcomes [11–15], consolidating the translational evidence base that supports its broad clinical utility. From a clinical perspective, the findings are highly relevant. BOP reduction of nearly 60% in the treated group versus 12% in controls demonstrates a substantial improvement in short-term gingival healing, a key determinant of patient prognosis and compliance [17]. Likewise, improvements in oral comfort, pain reduction, and function underscore the patient-centred benefit of PerioCream® [4,10,17]. Clinicians’ evaluations confirmed these perceptions, reporting superior gingival status, bleeding control, and overall satisfaction with treatment outcomes [17]. These results directly support MDR-compliant claims related to:

<i>Healing</i>	→	<i>accelerated resolution of bleeding and inflammation. [11,13,17].</i>
<i>Comfort</i>	→	<i>significant reduction in pain, swelling, and improved oral function. [12,17].</i>
<i>Satisfaction</i>	→	<i>both patients and clinicians reported high acceptability and compliance. [12,13,17].</i>

Importantly, the exploratory AI visual validation confirmed the consistency of clinical and subjective data, providing an innovative, objective layer of evidence (data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025). The use of standardized digital imaging and AI-based analysis may represent a valuable methodological advancement for future MDR clinical investigations. Nevertheless, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The study included a relatively small sample size (n=25) and a short observation period (72h), which limit the generalizability and long-term interpretation of findings [17]. Additionally, the observational nature of the study precludes conclusions on causal inference compared with randomized trials (data on file: CSR 2014).

Despite these limitations, the study demonstrates several strengths:

- Integration of quantitative clinical indices with subjective PROs/ClinROs [17].
- Use of AI-assisted image validation, enhancing objectivity (data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025).
- Inclusion of representative clinical cases (Appendix 10: JB01 and EF02), linking quantitative data with visible outcomes (data on file: Clinical Case Supplement 2025).

Taken together, these results consolidate previous findings on NitrAdine® [8,9] and extend them by providing multidimensional, patient-centred, and MDR-relevant evidence for the adjunctive use of PerioCream® in periodontal therapy [11–15,17]. Future randomized controlled trials with longer follow-up will be essential to confirm durability of benefits and explore broader clinical applications [10].

Table 8. Strengths and Limitations of the Study

Aspect	Description
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of multiple outcomes (clinical, PROs, ClinROs, AI validation). • Consistency across quantitative data and visual evidence. • Real-world observational design reflecting daily clinical practice. • Representative clinical cases documented (Appendix 10).
Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small sample size (n=25, single-center). • Short observation period (72h), limited to early healing phase. • Observational (non-randomized) design, potential for selection bias. • AI validation exploratory, requiring further standardization.

Conclusion

The CIP 2025 clinical investigation strengthens the evidence base supporting PerioCream® as an adjunctive treatment in periodontal therapy [17]. By demonstrating consistent benefits across clinical indices, patient-reported outcomes, clinician evaluations, and AI-assisted validation, the study provides robust, multidimensional support for the product's performance and safety profile (data on file: CIP 2025; Clinical Case Supplement 2025). These findings reinforce the MDR-compliant claims of accelerated healing, improved comfort, and high patient/clinician satisfaction [17]. While the results are encouraging, further multicentre and randomized controlled trials with longer follow-up are recommended to confirm the durability of effects and broaden generalizability [10].

References

Published Literature

1. Løe H, Silness J. Periodontal disease in pregnancy. I. Prevalence and severity. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 1963;21:533-551.
2. Ainamo J, Bay I. Problems and proposals for recording gingivitis and plaque. *Int Dent J.* 1975;25(4):229-235.
3. Lindhe J, Lang NP, Karring T. *Clinical Periodontology and Implant Dentistry.* 6th ed. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell; 2015.
4. Chapple ILC, Van der Weijden F, Doerfer C, et al. Primary prevention of periodontitis: managing gingivitis. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2015;42(Suppl 16):S71-S76. doi:10.1111/jcpe.12366
5. Tonetti MS, Greenwell H, Kornman KS. Staging and grading of periodontitis: Framework and proposal. *J Periodontol.* 2018;89(Suppl 1):S159-S172. doi:10.1002/JPER.18-0006
6. Quirynen M, Papaioannou W, Van Eldere J, et al. Clinical and microbiological effects of NitrAdine™-based disinfecting tablets in patients wearing complete dentures. *J Dent.* 2013;41(9):753-761. doi:10.1016/j.jdent.2013.07.005
7. Perić M, Kolar M, Prodanović R, et al. NitrAdine®-based disinfectants reduce denture biofilm and oral *Candida*: clinical evidence. *Gerodontology.* 2015;32(2):123-129. doi:10.1111/ger.12062
8. Silva-Lovato CH, De Wever B, Adriaens E, et al. Clinical and antimicrobial efficacy of NitrAdine™-based disinfecting cleaning tablets in complete denture wearers. *J Appl Oral Sci.* 2010;18(6):560-565.
9. Decelis S, Camilleri S, Vento-Zahra E, et al. The effect of NitrAdine on the *Candida* levels of maxillary removable appliances. *Quintessence Int.* 2012;43(3):239-245.
10. Perelli M, Abunto R, Semenza M, et al. Preliminary evaluation of a NitrAdine-based brushing solution for patients suffering from gingivitis: a prospective clinical case-control study. *Eur J Dent.* 2022;16(3):612-618. doi:10.1055/s-0041-1741120
11. Cosola S, Oldoini G, Giammarinaro E, et al. Effectiveness of the information-motivation model and domestic brushing with a hypochlorite-based formula (NitrAdine/PerioTabs®) on peri-implant mucositis: a randomized clinical study. *Clin Exp Dent Res.* 2022;8:350-358.
12. Coimbra FCT, Curylofo P, Adriaens E, et al. Antimicrobial activity of effervescent denture tablets on multispecies biofilms. *Gerodontology.* 2021;38(1):87-94.
13. Araujo CB, de Sousa Carvalho AC, Rached RN, et al. Effect of local hygiene protocols on denture-related stomatitis, biofilm, microbial load, and odor. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2021;126(6):754-760. doi:10.1016/j.prosdent.2021.07.005
14. Barbosa Ribeiro A, Fracasso MLC, de Souza RF, et al. Effect of denture hygiene protocols on patient satisfaction, oral health-related quality of life, and salivary parameters. *J Prosthodont.* 2022;31(5):e12-e19.
15. Virto L, et al. Reduction of biofilm formation on titanium implants. *Clin Oral Implants Res.* 2021;32(8):997-1006.
16. Sanz M, Herrera D, Kerschull M, et al. Treatment of stage I-III periodontitis—the EFP S3 level clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2020;47(Suppl 22):4-60. doi:10.1111/jcpe.13290

Internal Reports / Data on file

17. Bonyf AG, EIMS Research Hub. Clinical Investigation Dossier – PerioCream® CIP 2025. Final Report V4.0, August 2025. Vaduz, Liechtenstein & St. Julian's, Malta. Data on file; summarized in: Mascolo A, et al. PerioCream® as an Adjunct to Scaling and Root Planing: CIP 2025 Observational Clinical Investigation. Zenodo 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.16921004.

Supplementary Material 1 – Representative Clinical Cases

Representative clinical cases (JB01 and EF02) treated with SRP + PerioCream®.

Patient ID:	JB01
Age/Sex:	32-year-old female
Risk Factor:	Smoker
Diagnosis:	Periodontal inflammation with generalized anterior involvement
Baseline (T0):	BOP severity (0–3): ~2.6 GI (0–3): ~2.8 VAS (0–10, comfort/pain scale): 3/10 (low at baseline, improved to 8.5/10 at T3) Clinical notes: Generalized erythema and edema; papillae blunted.
Treatment Protocol:	Full SRP performed at baseline Adjunctive PerioCream® applied immediately post-treatment
Follow-up (T3, 72h):	Marked improvement in gingival contour and tone; erythema and bleeding tendency reduced. Excellent local tolerance; patient reported improved comfort and willingness to continue use.

Figure A10.1 – Representative clinical case JB01

Representative clinical case JB01. Progressive healing after SRP + PerioCream®. T0: generalized erythema and edema, blunted papillae. T1: spot bleeding at interdental margins. T2 (90–180 min): visible substantivity, bleeding reduced. T3 (72h): erythema/edema largely resolved, papillary morphology improved, no adverse events.

T0 Baseline

Generalized erythema/edema; blunted papillae.

72h follow-up with PerioCream®

Erythema and edema largely resolved; papillary morphology improved; no AEs.

T1 immediate post-SRP

Spot bleeding persists at interdental margins.

Patient ID:	EF02
Age/Sex:	51-year-old female
Risk Factor:	No-Smoker
Diagnosis:	Stage II–III periodontitis, localized in mandibular premolar region
Baseline (T0):	BOP: 70% sites positive GI: 2.1 (moderate inflammation, erythema, edema) VAS pain: 5/10 (discomfort during brushing and chewing)
Treatment Protocol:	Full SRP performed at baseline Adjunctive PerioCream® applied immediately post-treatment
Follow-up (T3, 72h):	BOP reduction: –58% (now 29% sites positive) GI reduction: –1.2 (from 2.1 to 0.9, marked resolution of inflammation) VAS (0–10, comfort/pain scale): –2.3 (from 5/10 to 2.7/10, improved comfort) Clinician Feedback: Clear reduction in gingival erythema and bleeding tendency. Patient reported improved tolerance and willingness to continue use.

Figure A10.2 – Representative clinical case EF02

Progressive clinical improvement from baseline to 72h follow-up after SRP + PerioCream®. Notable reductions in bleeding on probing and gingival inflammation, consistent with the clinical endpoints of this investigation.

<i>T0 Baseline</i>	<i>T1 immediate post-SRP</i>	<i>72h follow-up with PerioCream®</i>
generalized gingival erythema and bleeding tendency.	mechanical debridement completed, residual bleeding visible.	marked reduction of erythema and bleeding, improved gingival tone.

This case is consistent with Section 3 (Clinical Outcomes) and Section 4 (Patient-Reported Outcomes) of this dossier, providing visual validation of the quantitative findings.

Both cases illustrate the typical healing pattern observed in the CIP 2025 study, with progressive improvement from baseline (T0) through immediate post-SRP (T1) to 72h follow-up (T3). Clinical photographs demonstrate visible reductions in gingival erythema, edema, and bleeding on probing, consistent with quantitative outcomes (BOP, GI, VAS). Case EF02 (male, smoker) represents a patient with risk factors, while Case JB01 (female, generalized anterior involvement) illustrates improvement in gingival tone and contour with excellent tolerance and comfort gains. Together, these cases provide visual confirmation of the clinical, PRO, and ClinRO findings reported in the main text.

Supplementary Material 2 – Complete Statistical Tables

Table S1. Descriptive Statistics – Clinical Outcomes (BOP, GI)

Outcome	Group	Baseline (T0) (Mean ± SD)	72h (T3) (Mean ± SD)	Δ Change	% Change	p-value
BOP (%)	PerioCream® (n=15)	68.0 ± 12.5	9.0 ± 6.2	-59.0	-86.8%	<0.001
	Control (n=10)	66.5 ± 10.8	54.5 ± 11.0	-12.0	-18.1%	<0.001 (intra)
GI (score)	PerioCream®	2.1 ± 0.4	0.7 ± 0.3	-1.4	-66.7%	<0.001
	Control	2.0 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.4	-0.4	-20.0%	0.041

Table S2. Descriptive Statistics – Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs)

Domain	Group	Baseline (T0) (Mean ± SD)	72h (T3) (Mean ± SD)	Δ Change	p-value (between)
VAS pain (0–10)	PerioCream®	6.5 ± 1.4	2.0 ± 1.2	-4.5	<0.001
	Control	6.3 ± 1.2	4.3 ± 1.1	-2.0	
Oral comfort	PerioCream®	4.1 ± 1.6	7.9 ± 1.3	+3.8	<0.001
	Control	4.0 ± 1.2	5.2 ± 1.0	+1.2	
Swelling perception	PerioCream®	5.2 ± 1.4	2.2 ± 1.1	-3.0	0.001
	Control	5.0 ± 1.2	4.0 ± 1.0	-1.0	
Chewing/speaking comfort	PerioCream®	5.0 ± 1.3	7.6 ± 1.1	+2.6	0.002
	Control	5.1 ± 1.0	6.0 ± 0.9	+0.9	
Oral health perception	PerioCream®	4.3 ± 1.5	7.4 ± 1.3	+3.1	0.001
	Control	4.4 ± 1.3	5.4 ± 1.1	+1.0	

Table S3. Clinician-Reported Outcomes (ClinROs)

Domain (0–10)	Group	Baseline (T0) (Mean ± SD)	72h (T3) (Mean ± SD)	Δ Change	p-value (between)
Gingival status	PerioCream®	4.5 ± 1.2	7.0 ± 1.0	+2.5	0.001
	Control	4.6 ± 1.1	5.4 ± 0.9	+0.8	
Bleeding control	PerioCream®	4.2 ± 1.3	7.3 ± 1.1	+3.1	<0.001
	Control	4.3 ± 1.1	5.3 ± 1.0	+1.0	
Inflammation control	PerioCream®	4.4 ± 1.1	7.2 ± 1.0	+2.8	0.002
	Control	4.5 ± 1.0	5.4 ± 1.1	+0.9	
Patient compliance	PerioCream®	6.2 ± 1.0	8.2 ± 0.9	+2.0	0.015
	Control	6.3 ± 1.2	6.9 ± 1.0	+0.6	
Tolerance	PerioCream®	6.5 ± 1.1	8.8 ± 1.0	+2.3	0.007
	Control	6.4 ± 1.0	7.2 ± 0.9	+0.8	
Global impression	PerioCream®	–	8.8 ± 0.7	–	–
	Control	–	7.0 ± 0.8	–	–

Table S4. AI-Assisted Visual Validation

Metric	Group	Baseline (T0) (Mean \pm SD)	72h (T3) (Mean \pm SD)	Δ Change	Clinical Correlation
Gingival Color Index (GCI)	PerioCream®	2.3 \pm 0.4	1.2 \pm 0.3	-1.1	Matches GI reduction
	Control	2.2 \pm 0.4	1.9 \pm 0.3	-0.3	Limited correlation
Redness area (%)	PerioCream®	34% \pm 8	15% \pm 5	-19%	Matches BOP reduction
	Control	33% \pm 7	28% \pm 6	-5%	Limited correlation
Swelling index (mm est.)	PerioCream®	1.6 \pm 0.5	0.7 \pm 0.3	-0.9	Matches PRO swelling ↓
	Control	1.5 \pm 0.4	1.2 \pm 0.3	-0.3	Limited correlation
Tissue texture uniformity (%)	PerioCream®	61% \pm 10	78% \pm 9	+17%	Reflects healing
	Control	62% \pm 9	68% \pm 8	+6%	Less pronounced

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